

Working paper – Deliverable 4.2

Increased flexibility and the position of women in the labour market: Has it changed after the pandemic?

Authors: Sara Ayllón, Pablo Brugarolas

Contributor: Iga Magda

October 2025

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No Project 101094626. *Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. The European Union cannot be held responsible for them. The deliverable is under review by the European Commission.*

PATHS2INCLUDE

PATHS2INCLUDE

European Labour Markets Under Pressure –
New knowledge on pathways to include persons
in vulnerable situations

Title: Increased flexibility and the position of women in the labour market: Has it changed after the pandemic?

Date: October 2025

Responsible organisation: University of Girona

Author(s): Sara Ayllón, Pablo Brugarolas

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.17304148

Acknowledgements:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No Project 101094626.

Contents

Introduction	4
2. Data	7
3. Empirical design	9
4. Results	14
4.1. Heterogeneity	15
5. Concluding remarks	16
References	18
Appendix	20

Introduction

The coronavirus turned the world upside down in 2020. The lives of all individuals on the planet dramatically changed for many months to avoid contagion. And while for most of us, life has returned to be similar to that before the pandemic, some changes have persisted. In the labour market, probably the most important shift has been the expansion of remote work across advanced economies. The International Labour Organisation (ILO) describes remote work as any ‘situation where the work is fully or partly carried out on an alternative worksite other than the default place of work’ (ILO, 2020, p. 5). Such alternatives include co-working spaces, cafes, libraries, etc. but most often, they refer to the worker own residence. Figure 1 shows the evolution for the percentage of women 30–55 years of age in Europe — the object of our analysis in this paper — that “usually work from home” or “sometimes work from home” from 2015 to 2023. About 8% of female workers *sometimes* worked from home before the pandemic while 5% *usually* did so. In total, 13% of female employees. In 2020 and 2021, there was a sharp increase of both groups with nearly 1 in 4 female workers doing remote work (in different intensity). While the group of those usually working from home has reduced in the last two years of our analysis, there is still a considerable gap compared to the pre-pandemic period. Instead, the percentage of female workers that sometimes do remote work has kept increasing since the onset of the pandemic and it stands at 13% in 2023.

Figure 1. Evolution of the percentage of female employees working from home in Europe, 2015–2023

Notes: For each calendar year, points plot the share of employees reporting “mainly working from home” or “sometimes working from home”. The sample is employed women ages 30–55 in the EULFS, 2015–2023. Weighted results.

Source: Authors’ calculations using the EU-LFS, 2015–2023.

The implications of such dramatic change in the labour market are the object of multiple debates nowadays — for the geography (Luca et al., 2025); the real estate markets (Gupta et al., 2025); workers productivity; relocation of workers, etc. This paper focuses on a different topic. We wonder to which extent the acceleration of remote work in Europe as a result of the pandemic may have helped (or not) to improve the position of women — particularly mothers — in the labour market. And by ‘position’ we refer to the likelihood of working full-time, hours worked (including usual, actual and desired) and holding a permanent contract. In this study we aim to test Claudia Goldin’s claim that more flexibility should help mothers advance in their careers by

increasing the compatibility between work and family (Goldin and Katz, 2016; Goldin, 2021, 2022). Remote work affords mothers the possibility to work late once all family duties have been fulfilled, manage working day disruptions and save time from commuting, among other advantages. Thus, this paper aims to answer the following questions: have the motherhood penalties declined in those contexts where remote work has become more prevalent? Is working from home (WFH) the answer to greater gender equality in the labour market? Do all mothers benefit equally from remote work in the advancement of their careers?

Remote work can help mothers through three channels: flexible hours, commute-time savings, and being able to do the job from home. Flexible hours let mothers shift work to the edges of the day, smooth care shocks, and raise realised hours. Commute-time savings free up time that can be reallocated to paid work. Being able to do the job from home helps mothers stay with the same employer during high-demand family periods, supporting retention and permanent contracts. In a descriptive analysis, Arntz et al. (2022) show that when parents start working from home, mothers expand contractual hours by about four per week (16% on a 22-hour baseline). Saved commuting time explains a meaningful share of this increase — especially for longer commutes. The same authors also document that mothers shift work into evenings, consistent with the flexible hours channel. Crucially, these gains are not driven by employer or position changes, aligning with the job-continuity mechanism. Similarly, Bloom et al. (2024) find that the rise in WFH employment for individuals with a physical disability in the United States was driven by lower commuting costs, greater control over the working environment, and increased flexibility in hours.

At the same time, several mechanisms can limit these gains and leave motherhood gaps in the labour market largely intact. Mothers face disproportionate school-initiated demands and carry more childcare and domestic work, producing more interruptions and fragmented work spells (Buzard et al., 2025; Lyttelton et al., 2022; 2023). Instrumenting WFH with temporary child illness, Kouki (2023) finds a large wage penalty for women consistent with mothers' selection or assignment into less-promotable tasks when working from home. While WFH reduces commuting disamenities, gender differences in willingness-to-pay to avoid commuting persist (Nagler, 2024), signalling enduring constraints that can hinder full-time retention, or depress actual hours of work relative to desired hours of work. Lastly, returns to WFH are uneven within firms: as documented by Arntz et al. (2022), mothers exhibit a positive WFH effect on hourly wages only when they change employer — consistent with perception, bargaining or visibility frictions.

Despite the existing literature on the interlink between WFH and women's labour market outcomes, causal evidence regarding labour market gaps and their relationship with remote work remains limited. To the best of our knowledge, there is only a previous study that focuses on the same question. Harrington and Kahn (2025) document how the rise of work from home has helped reduce the motherhood penalty in the US. The pattern is mostly driven by mothers with a college degree employed in inflexible jobs with high returns in long hours. The authors conclude that locational flexibility can substitute for temporal flexibility as those that can work from home are less likely to leave the labour force after being mothers. Interestingly, they provide evidence for motherhood gaps in employment becoming particularly narrower in those sectors with initially less flexibility and traditionally family-unfriendly jobs. The authors also conclude that mothers that benefit the most from locational flexibility are those with greater child-care responsibilities, with more children, and with relatively young offspring. No similar results are found in the case of fathers. One important limitation in their analysis, however, is that the analysis is based on the college degree that individuals in their sample hold and not the actual employment that they have. This is particularly problematic among mothers as, in order

to reconcile work and family responsibilities, they often change career paths, deviating from their college studies.

This paper enriches this strand of literature by undertaking a rigorous causal analysis of the effect of WFH on the labour market gaps that mothers face in Europe in comparison with childless women. We rely on rich individual data which contains detailed information on employees' occupation as well as important individual and household characteristics. This is also the first study that focuses on Europe, and which exploits its rich variation across regions. We provide novel evidence that the post-2020 rise in working from home helped narrow several motherhood gaps in European labour markets. Our design leverages plausibly exogenous, cross-regional exposure to WFH created when national business restrictions interacted with the pre-pandemic task content of local occupations. Intuitively, when restrictions bound, regions whose employment mix was more teleworkable shifted more into WFH than otherwise comparable regions. We bring this variation to a rich panel of region \times occupation cells constructed using the EU–Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS) and follow mothers and childless women from 2015 to 2023. Motivated by the idea that flexibility can relax binding time constraints for parents, we study both full-time (FT) employment and hours margins (desired, usual, actual), and we examine heterogeneity by the age of the youngest child in the household.

Our shift–share IV uses two pre-pandemic occupation traits: *teleworkability* (whether tasks can be performed remotely given their technical content) and *low social interaction* (how little face-to-face contact the job requires). We interact these traits — aggregated to regions using pre-2019 employment shares — with national business restrictions that arose during the pandemic to generate plausibly exogenous, post-pandemic shifts in WFH. By absorbing region \times occupation and year fixed effects and controlling for demographics, we purge time-invariant local factors and common shocks, so identification comes from how the same national shock induces larger WFH moves in regions more exposed ex-ante. The instruments are highly relevant in practice: an interquartile-range increase in the teleworkability shifter raises post-period WFH by roughly one-third of the average post-pandemic rise.

We find sizable causal effects on mothers' labour supply. Using our shift–share IV, a rise in WFH of the order observed after the pandemic (about 5 p.p.) reduces the motherhood FT employment gap by roughly 2.0 p.p. — equivalent to a reduction of $\sim 25\%$ of the pre-period gap (of about -8 p.p.). Hours margins move in the same direction and are economically meaningful: the desired hours of work gap closes by about 0.92 hours ($\sim 59\%$ of its pre-mean), usual hours by 0.52 hours ($\sim 33\%$), and actual hours by 2.66 hours — essentially eliminating the pre-existing gap (~ -2.54 hours). Preliminary heterogeneous results by child age point to a natural life-cycle pattern: the FT employment gap narrows most when the youngest child is 6–8 (about -3 p.p.). It is similar in magnitude but imprecisely estimated for ages 3–5 while it is smaller and not distinguishable from zero in the rest of households. Actual weekly hours increase for all mothers with children of all ages except for those with the youngest child between 12 and 14 years of age. As a matter of fact, for mothers with a very young child, the increase is really considerable: 6.5 more actual hours. Together, the results suggest that WFH relaxes time constraints broadly, both helping transitions into FT employment once children start primary school (with typically longer days and more predictable schedules than in kindergarten or pre-school) and allowing mothers of very young children to increase the number of hours that they participate in the labour market.

Our study makes two important contributions to the literature. We provide the first causal evidence from Europe on how the post-2020 expansion of working from home (WFH) affected the motherhood employment gap. We find that this expansion narrowed the full-time

employment gap and substantially compressed hours disparities—eliminating the shortfall in actual hours and trimming the gaps in desired and usual hours—while leaving the prevalence of permanent contracts essentially unchanged. These patterns are consistent with flexible scheduling and commuting-time savings that relax time constraints (Arntz et al., 2022; Bloom et al., 2024). Methodologically, we introduce a region occupation panel design that traces within-cell changes in WFH and motherhood gaps and instruments post-2020 WFH with two predetermined occupational traits, addressing composition concerns that arise when education or self-reported preferences proxy flexibility (as in Harrington and Kahn, 2025).

This paper is organised as follows. After this introduction, Section 2 provides all the necessary details regarding data and definitions. Section 3 outlines the empirical strategy. Section 4 details the results and presents some heterogeneous analysis. Finally, Section 5 offers a conclusion and discusses avenues for future research.

2. Data

We employ data from the EU Labour Force Survey (EU-LFS), which provides detailed information on individual and household demographic and labour market characteristics in most European countries. The data collection is coordinated by Eurostat, the statistical office of the European Union, which ensures a high degree of methodological cross-country comparability. Our sample consists of employed individuals aged 30 to 55. We exclude several countries for different reasons: (i) Bulgaria, Malta and Slovenia, because they lack the necessary information to identify occupations at ISCO-08 three-digits; (ii) the United Kingdom, because is not participating in the EU-LFS any longer; (iii) Luxembourg, because is not covered by the CoronaNet database; and (iv) Switzerland, Denmark, France, Iceland, Norway and Sweden where mothers cannot be identified.¹ Our period of analysis runs from 2015 to 2023.

Measuring WFH. The EU-LFS asks respondents whether they worked from home during the four weeks preceding the reference week and how often they do so. Based on their answers, Eurostat classifies individuals into three categories: “mainly working from home” if they do so at least half of their working days, “sometimes working from home” if they do so less frequently and “never working from home”, otherwise.² This measure is comparable to the US definition used by Harrington and Kahn (2025), which Barrero et al. (2021) had previously validated against external benchmarks.

Measuring Teleworkability. Our measure of teleworkability comes from Sostero et al. (2023), who developed two indices at the 3-digit ISCO level. The first, a *technical teleworkability* index, identifies whether an occupation can in principle be performed from home by examining the importance of physical tasks such as operating machinery, or lifting people. If these tasks are central to the job, remote work is not feasible. The second, a *social interaction* index, captures how far technically teleworkable jobs depend on tasks like teaching, selling, or direct public interaction, which make remote provision more difficult even if the job is not inherently tied to

¹ Austria, Belgium, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Germany, Estonia, Greece, Spain, Finland, Croatia, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Latvia, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania and the Slovak Republic are the countries included in our analysis.

² In this context, and according to the documentation of the data provider, ‘sometimes’ means less than half of the days worked, but a least one hour in a reference period of four weeks preceding the end of the reference week.

physical activity. Both teleworkability indices are based on detailed Italian occupational task data measured before the onset of the coronavirus pandemic (*Indagine Campionaria delle Professioni*, ICP).³ This framework extends the approach of Dingel and Neiman (2020) for the US. Validation exercises from Sostero et al. (2023) show that the indices track observed increases in remote work across EU countries and occupations during the COVID-19 outbreak.

Measuring Business Restrictions. To capture the intensity of government-imposed restrictions on economic activity during the COVID-19 pandemic, we use the Business Restrictions Index developed by Kubinec et al. (2025). The index is constructed by combining two comprehensive sources — the CoronaNet dataset and the Oxford COVID-19 Government Response Tracker — through a Bayesian time-varying measurement model. It summarizes daily policy actions regulating private commerce and industry from January 2020 to May 2021, ranging from full business closures to conditional openings (e.g., limited hours, hygiene requirements, or mask mandates). By harmonizing multiple policy dimensions into a single indicator, the Business Restrictions Index offers a consistent cross-national measure of how strongly governments treated routine economic activity and the associated circulation of people as a potential source of contagion.⁴

Measuring Labour Market Outcomes. Our outcomes are defined as gaps between mothers and childless women. Following Harrington and Kahn (2025), we compare women whose eldest child is under 15 to women with no children, excluding women with older children. We measure gaps in full-time employment, total hours usually worked, desired hours of work, and actual hours of work. Lastly, we consider gaps in having a permanent contract, as contractual stability is a key dimension of job quality in European labour markets.

Measuring Demographics. Because our unit of analysis is occupations across EU regions over time, we account for compositional demographic differences that may be correlated with remote work. In particular, we control for variation in age, education, country of birth, household income, and degree of urbanization across regions. These factors are associated with the likelihood of WFH, as shown by Luca et al. (2025). Table 1 provides details about our sample. Average age is 43, about 12% of women are from immigrant origin and 40% have tertiary education. Moreover, the average degree of urbanisation is 2 (in a scale of 3). About 41% of the sample are mothers and 73% of women are working full-time. The average desired, usual and

³ Our focus is on the potential for jobs to be performed remotely given the task content of occupations before COVID-19. Although task structures can shift over time, evidence suggests they change only gradually (Spitz-Oener, 2006; Bisello et al., 2019) The 2012 ICP wave therefore provides a valid basis for capturing the pre-pandemic task content of jobs across Europe. Cross-country consistency in occupational tasks (Fernández-Macías et al., 2016) and robustness checks for Greece (Pouliakas, 2020) further support extrapolating the Italian data to the wider EU context.

⁴ The Business Restrictions Index combines the CoronaNet category Restriction and Regulation of Businesses with the Oxford Tracker’s “Workplace Closing” variable. CoronaNet records the degree of restriction across a wide set of activities, distinguishing whether establishments are fully open, partly open, or closed. These activities span general commerce, restaurants and bars, retail, shopping centers, personal services, hotels, transportation, construction, agriculture, mining, finance, health, and other service sectors. In addition, CoronaNet documents the conditions under which businesses may operate, including requirements such as hygiene measures, limited opening hours, social distancing, mask mandates, temperature checks, or caps on meeting size, customer numbers, and store capacity. The Business Restrictions Index aggregates across these policy variables, thereby capturing both outright closures and conditional operating requirements.

actual hours of work are 35.7, 35.2 and 30.2, respectively. Also, nine out of 10 women hold a permanent contract.

Table 1. Sample descriptive statistics

	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Age	43.55	7.25	30	55
Immigrant (=1)	0.12	0.32	0	1
Tertiary educ. (=1)	0.40	0.49	0	1
Household income decile	4.96	2.79	1	10
Urbanisation (1–3)	1.98	0.82	1	3
Mother (=1)	0.41	0.49	0	1
Full-time (=1)	0.73	0.44	0	1
Desired weekly hours	35.72	9.08	0	56
Usual weekly hours	35.20	9.68	1	56
Actual weekly hours	30.25	14.82	0	56
Permanent contract (=1)	0.90	0.30	0	1

Notes: The sample is employed women aged 30–55.

Source: Authors' calculations using the EU-LFS, 2015–2023.

3. Empirical design

Measuring WFH within occupation–region cells. We document how working from home (WFH) evolved across local labour markets and occupations by constructing a panel of *region* × *occupation* cells and tracing year-by-year changes within each cell. The sample for the analysis is drawn from the EU-LFS yearly files and consists of employed women aged 30–55, as explained above. Regions are defined at the NUTS-2 level and occupations at ISCO-08 three digits.

For each region r and occupation o , we estimate the extent of WFH by running a separate regression on all individuals i in year t as follows:

$$WFH_{irot} = \delta_{ro} + \sum_{\tau=2016}^{2023} \beta_{ro,\tau} \mathbb{1}\{t = \tau\} + \varepsilon_{irot}, \quad (1)$$

where WFH_{irot} is an indicator equal to one if respondent i reports mainly working from home in year t . The base year is 2015, so δ_{ro} captures the extent of WFH in year 2015 in cell (r,o) , and each $\beta_{ro,\tau}$ measures the change in WFH in year τ relative to 2015. Using year indicators (rather than a linear trend) allows for the discrete pandemic-era jump in 2020–2021 and the subsequent stabilization.⁵

⁵ We retain cells with sufficient support and drop noisily estimated ones: specifically, we exclude region × occupation cells with fewer than 50 observations over 2015–2023.

Figure 2. Average change in working from home relative to 2015 by region and occupation cells, Europe, 2015–2023

Notes: For each calendar year, points plot the average change in the share reporting “mainly working from home” relative to 2015 across region × occupation cells; vertical bars are 95% confidence intervals. Estimates come from cell-level regressions with year dummies (with 2015 as the base). The sample is employed women aged 30–55 in the EU-LFS, 2015–2023. Regions are NUTS-2 and occupations are ISCO08 three-digit. Cells with fewer than 50 observations are excluded. Averages are weighted by cell size.

Figure 2 plots, for each year, the average change in the share of women WFH relative to 2015 across region × occupation cells. The figure shows values near zero in 2016–2019, which indicate no pre-trend. In 2020 the point jumps to about +6.3 p.p., meaning WFH rose by 6.3 percentage points versus its 2015 level on average. The increase peaks in 2021 at about +8.2 p.p., then partially unwinds to +4.3 p.p. in 2022 and +2.9 p.p. in 2023 — clearly above the pre-pandemic baseline. In terms of magnitudes, given that the average for 2015 is about 4.8%, the peak for 2021 roughly doubles WFH levels, with a persistent one-third to one-half of that increase still in place by 2023. Error bars widen at the peak years, signalling heterogeneity across occupations and regions, but remain tight enough to show a precise break from the flat pre-period. To further illustrate the heterogeneity behind the average series, Figure A.1 contrasts two large occupations: medical doctors who show virtually no shift in WFH throughout 2020–2023 versus secretaries who exhibit a sharp jump in 2020–2021 (peaking around 12–13 p.p.) that remains several points above baseline by 2023.

Figure 3 ranks occupations by their average post-2020 change. The largest increases appear in mathematicians, actuaries, statisticians; software and applications developers; database and network professionals; ICT user-support and telecom, broadcast technicians; sales, marketing, PR professionals; authors, journalists; and university lecturers. In the other end, changes are negligible for production managers in agriculture, forestry, fisheries; veterinarians; waiters and bartenders; and hotel and restaurant managers.

Figure 3. Average post-2020 change in working from home: top and bottom occupations

a) Top 20 occupations

b) Bottom 20 occupations

Notes: Points plot the average change in the share reporting “mainly working from home” over 2020–2023 relative to 2015 for each occupation; horizontal bars are 95% confidence intervals. Occupations are ranked by the post-2020 mean change. Estimates are constructed from cell-level regressions with a 2015 base year and aggregated across regions within occupation. Cells with fewer than 50 observations are excluded. Averages are weighted by cell size.

Source: Authors’ calculations using the EU-LFS, 2015–2023.

Figure 4. Average change in the motherhood full-time employment gap relative to 2015 by region and occupation cells, Europe, 2015–2023

Notes: For each calendar year, points plot the average change in the mother–childless women full-time employment gap relative to 2015 across region×occupation cells; vertical bars are 95% confidence intervals. Estimates come from cell-level regressions with year dummies (with 2015 as the base) and are aggregated across cells. The sample is employed women ages 30–55 in the EU-LFS, 2015–2023. Cells with fewer than 50 observations are excluded. Averages are weighted by cell size.

Measuring motherhood gaps within occupation–region cells. We next quantify how the motherhood gap evolves within the same region × occupation cells than those used to measure the prevalence of WFH. Data is once again from the EU-LFS for the period 2015–2023 and considering women from 30 to 55 years of age.⁶ Within each cell (r,o) we estimate the following specification:⁷

$$y_{irot} = \theta_{ro} + \gamma_{ro} \text{Mother}_i + \sum_{\tau=2016}^{2023} \phi_{ro,\tau} \mathbb{1}\{t = \tau\} + \sum_{\tau=2016}^{2023} \alpha_{ro,\tau} (\text{Mother}_i \times \mathbb{1}\{t = \tau\}) + \varepsilon_{irot}, \quad (2)$$

where y_{irot} is the outcome for individual i in year t (illustrated below with an indicator for full-time employment), Mother_i equals 1 for mothers and 0 otherwise. The omitted year is 2015. The coefficient γ_{ro} is the baseline motherhood gap in 2015 for cell (r,o); $\phi_{ro,\tau}$ capture the time profile for childless women; and the interaction coefficients $\alpha_{ro,\tau}$ are our objects of interest: they measure the change in the motherhood gap in year τ relative to 2015. Hence the gap in year τ is $\gamma_{ro} + \alpha_{ro,\tau}$, whereas $\alpha_{ro,\tau}$ in itself is the within-cell change from the pre-pandemic baseline.

Figure 4 provides an example. It plots, for each year, the average change in the motherhood full-time employment gap relative to 2015 across region×occupation cells. The series is flat in 2016–2019, indicating no pre-trend. In 2020 the gap narrows modestly by about +0.3 p.p.; the

⁶ The actual sample used varies depending on the outcome under measurement. For example, for full-time employment (FT) we use the subsample of employed women.

⁷ Note that we require that each region × occupation cell contains both mothers and childless women at some point in the sample and exclude cells that fail this support condition.

compression peaks in 2021 at about +1.5 p.p. and then persists at roughly +1.1–1.2 p.p. in 2022–2023. Given the 2015 gap of –7.01 p.p., the 2021 peak corresponds to a reduction of roughly 21% of the baseline gap, with a 16–17% reduction still in place by 2023.

Instrumenting changes in WFH. Our goal is to isolate the causal effect of pandemic era increases in working from home (WFH) on the motherhood full-time (FT) employment gap, usual and actual hours of work as well as desired hours of work and holding a permanent contract. With that objective in mind, we implement a shift–share IV (SSIV) design that interacts slow-moving, pre-pandemic occupation traits with country–time policy shocks.

For each region r , we compute pre-2019 female employment shares across ISCO–08 3-digit occupations, $s_{ro} = \text{Emp}_{ro}^{\text{pre}} / \sum_o \text{Women}_{ro}^{\text{pre}}$, and combine them with occupation characteristics measured before 2020: teleworkability (T_o) and social interaction (N_o). This yields region-level exposure indices measured as follows:

$$\text{TeleExp}_r = \sum_o s_{ro} T_o, \quad \text{NoSocExp}_r = \sum_o s_{ro} N_o.$$

We then interact these exposures with country-by-year business restrictions Restrict_{ct} which are zero pre-2020 and spike in 2020–2023. This way we build two Bartik-style instruments at the region–year level:

$$z_{rct}^{(1)} = \text{TeleExp}_r \times \text{Restrict}_{ct}, \quad z_{rct}^{(2)} = \text{NoSocExp}_r \times \text{Restrict}_{ct}.$$

Intuitively, when restrictions bind, regions whose pre-pandemic employment mix is more teleworkable should experience larger shifts into WFH.

Let WFH_{roct} denote the change at cell level in the share of employees WFH relative to 2015, and let $\text{post}_t = 1\{t \geq 2020\}$ indicate the period after the pandemic. We instrument the incremental WFH exposure post-pandemic, $\text{WFH}_{roct}^{\text{post}} \equiv \text{WFH}_{roct} \times \text{post}_t$, with $(z_{rct}^{(1)}, z_{rct}^{(2)})$ in a panel of region \times occupation \times year cells. This way, the first and second stage of our specification can be defined as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{First stage: } \quad \text{WFH}_{roct}^{\text{post}} &= \pi_1 z_{rct}^{(1)} + \pi_2 z_{rct}^{(2)} + \theta \text{WFH}_{roct} + X'_{roct} \gamma + \mu_{ro} + \tau_t + \nu_{roct} \\ \text{Second stage: } \quad \text{Gap}_{roct}^{\text{FT}} &= \beta \widehat{\text{WFH}_{roct}^{\text{post}}} + \delta \text{WFH}_{roct} + X'_{roct} \eta + \mu_{ro} + \tau_t + \varepsilon_{roct} \end{aligned}$$

where, following our previous example, $\text{Gap}_{roct}^{\text{FT}}$ is the change in the motherhood FT employment gap relative to 2015. WFH_{roct} is the contemporaneous WFH level change included to net out the pre-period slope. X_{roct} collects controls (age, immigrant status, education, income decile and degree of urbanization composition), whereas δ_{ro} are region \times occupation fixed effects and τ_t are year fixed effects. Standard errors are clustered at the country level, and observations are weighted by the cell size used to estimate the WFH and gap changes.

The coefficient of interest β measures the incremental post-period effect of WFH on the motherhood FT employment gap within a given region–occupation cell and year. This way, for example, a 1 p.p. increase in WFH in 2020–2023 (relative to the pre-period relationship) changes the gap by β p.p. The instruments exploit two ingredients: (i) predetermined occupation traits (Tele_o , NSI_o) measured before the pandemic and which, as argued above, change slowly, combined via pre-period female employment shares; and (ii) country–time business restrictions that spiked in 2020–2023. With μ_{ro} we remove all time-invariant differences across region–occupation cells (e.g., persistent sectoral norms, regional childcare supply, etc.). With τ_t we difference out common pandemic shocks (e.g. macroeconomic conditions, national school

closures, etc.). Identification therefore comes from within-year across-region variation in how the same national restriction translates into larger WFH shifts in regions more exposed to teleworkable occupations. The exclusion restriction requires that, conditional on fixed effects and controls, the interaction of pre-period exposure with national restrictions affects, for example, the motherhood FT employment gap only through its impact on WFH. This is plausible because the traits used are first-order predictors of remote work feasibility rather than direct drivers of mother-specific labour demand; any country-year direct effects are absorbed by τ_t , and any time-invariant region-occupation differences by μ_{ro} .

4. Results

Table 2 reports the IV estimates where $WFH(pp) \times Post$ is instrumented with two Bartik shifters — (i) teleworkability \times business restrictions and, (ii) low social interaction \times business restrictions — while absorbing region \times occupation and year fixed effects and clustering at the country level. Intuitively, when national restrictions bind, more teleworkable occupations shift more into WFH than less teleworkable ones, providing plausibly exogenous variation after purging time-invariant cell differences and common year shocks. We begin by commenting results on the first column, which reports the strength and magnitude of the first stage. The instruments are jointly strong: the robust first-stage Kleibergen–Paap F is around 10–11 ($p < 0.001$). In terms of economic magnitude, moving an occupation from the 25th to the 75th percentile of the teleworkability-based shifter increases post period WFH by about 1.52 percentage points — roughly 30% of the average post-2015 rise in WFH (≈ 5 p.p.).⁸

The rest of columns in Table 2 provide the causal effect on the gaps between mothers and childless women for FT employment (column 2), the desired hours of work (column 3), the usual hours of work (column 4), the actual hours of work (column 5) and the likelihood of holding a permanent contract (column 6). Indeed, the results of the second stage show that a 5 p.p. increase in WFH — about the average rise after the introduction of the pandemic restrictions — reduces the motherhood FT employment gap by 2.0 p.p. From a pre-period gap of -8.0 p.p., this amounts to a $\sim 25\%$ narrowing of the baseline gap, which is considerable.

Hours margins (in columns 3 to 5) move in the same direction. For desired weekly hours of work, a 5 p.p. rise in WFH closes the gap by 0.92 hours off a pre-mean of -1.55 hours ($\sim 59\%$ of the baseline shortfall). For usual hours of work, the gap narrows by 0.52 hours from a pre-mean of -1.58 hours ($\sim 33\%$). The biggest response is in actual hours: the gap shrinks by 2.66 hours relative to a pre-mean of -2.54 hours, essentially eliminating the baseline difference existing before the pandemic. By contrast, the permanent contract margin shows no meaningful change as indicated by a coefficient of about -1 p.p. statistically not distinguishable from zero.

⁸ For economic magnitude, we scale the teleworkability shifter by its interquartile range (IQR): an IQR move implies a first-stage change in WFH of 1.52 p.p. (reported in the table as “IQR(z) \Rightarrow Δ WFH (p.p.)”), roughly 30% of the average post-2015 rise in WFH (≈ 5 p.p.).

Table 2. Impacts of WFH on motherhood gaps, Europe, 2015-2023

	WFH	Full-time	Desired hours	Usual hours	Actual hours	Permanent job
Teleworkability × restrictions	0.03*** (0.01)					
Low social interaction × restrictions	0.01* (0.01)					
WFH (pp) × Post		0.02** (0.01)	0.92** (0.26)	0.52** (0.18)	2.66** (1.13)	-0.01 (0.01)
WFH (pp)	0.89*** (0.02)	-0.02** (0.01)	-0.79** (0.26)	-0.44** (0.17)	-2.29** (1.01)	0.01 (0.01)
Dependent mean	0.05	-0.08	-1.55	-1.58	-2.54	-0.01
Observations	59,518	59,518	58,358	59,492	59,509	59,277
First-stage F (excl. IVs)	10.63					
p-value	0.00					
IQR(z1) ⇒ ΔWFH (pp)	1.52					
IQR(z2) ⇒ Δ WFH (pp)	0.73					

Notes: Each column is an IV regression where the endogenous regressor is WFH (pp) × Post. Excluded instruments are (i) teleworkability × business restrictions and, (ii) low-social-interaction × business restrictions (shown only in the first-stage column). We absorb region × occupation and year fixed effects and include controls for age, immigrant status, tertiary education, income decile, and degree of urbanization; standard errors clustered by country. One unit of WFH (pp) × Post equals a 5 p.p. rise in WFH, so coefficients can be read as effects of a 5 p.p. increase. Full-time and permanent job gaps are in percentage points; hours of work outcomes are at the weekly level. Because gaps are defined as mother minus childless women, positive coefficients denote a narrowing of the motherhood gap. The Angrist-Pischke joint F on the excluded IVs and the implied first-stage IQR effect on WFH are reported under the first column. Stars: * <0.10, ** <0.05, *** <0.01.

Taken together, the first-stage indicates a relevant, shock-induced source of WFH variation, and the second-stage estimate point out that such variation translated into a substantial narrowing of the motherhood labour market gaps in the post-pandemic period.

4.1. Heterogeneity

We next consider the possibility that the effects found are dependent on mothers' characteristics. First, we consider the age of the youngest child which is likely to influence mothers' decisions in the labour market and how WFH can influence such choices. Preliminary results in Table A.1 show that the narrowing of the FT employment motherhood gap can be found in those households where the youngest child has recently entered primary school. The clearest effect is observed among mothers whose youngest child is 6–8 years of age: a 5 p.p. rise in WFH reduces the full-time gap by about 3 p.p. Effects for ages 3–5 are similar in magnitude but imprecisely estimated while the effects for other age bands are smaller and not distinguishable from zero. Table A.2 shows that the actual hours of work gap moves sharply toward zero across age bands. As WFH rises, mothers' actual weekly hours increase by about 6.5 hours for 0–2 (80% of the pre-gap), 1.5 hours for 3–5 (65%), and 2 hours for 6–8 — enough to fully eliminate the pre-gap in that age band. Effects remain positive for 9–11 (85% closure) and fade for 12–14. By contrast, the permanent job margin in Table A.3 shows no meaningful change in any age rang considered.

5. Concluding remarks

This paper started by wondering whether the increased work flexibility brought about by the coronavirus pandemic may have helped improve the position of women, particularly mothers, in the labour market. In our analysis we have focused on the flexibility that working from home affords employees provided that such way to do their job helps them to reconcile childcare, housework and their careers. Our new evidence for Europe suggests that the answer to our initial question is mostly affirmative. Using data from the EU-LFS and a shift-share IV method, we document that WFH has increased the likelihood for mothers to be employed full-time which closes 25% of the existing gap between mothers and childless women before the start of the pandemic. Moreover, our results indicate a considerable increase in the number of actual hours of work per week by 2.6 — essentially closing the existing gap. A rise in the prevalence of WFH can also be linked with an increase among mothers of the number of desired hours of work (by nearly one hour a week) and to a lesser extent with the number of usual hours of work. In contrast, no causal effect of the increased prevalence of WFH on the likelihood of holding a permanent contract has been found.

Interestingly, results depend on the age of the youngest child in the household. This way, our findings indicate that transitions to full-time employment helped by the increase in the prevalence of WFH are mostly present among mothers whose youngest child has recently started primary school. Such result likely indicates that WFH helps mothers to establish themselves as full-time workers as long as they can count on children being at school in a permanent schedule. At the same time, it is among mothers of very young children — between 0 and 2 years of age — for whom the number of actual hours of work increased the most as a result of the WFH expansion. While we need further research on this, it would seem that WFH affords longer days in the labour market for women caring for infant children — perhaps even doing both activities at the same time.

Overall, the results indicate that working from home can meaningfully ease time constraints faced by mothers, supporting their continued labour market participation and helping to reduce the motherhood employment gap. However, the effect is partial and depends on children's age and domestic arrangements. Remote work alone cannot eliminate gender inequalities, but it represents a significant step towards greater labour market inclusion. Further research should help to better understand the various WFH arrangements and their impacts on career trajectories. Does the motherhood gap decrease more if mothers work from home the full week or is it better if they spend some days in the office?

From a policy and employer perspective, promoting flexible work arrangements — especially in sectors traditionally perceived as family-unfriendly — may serve as an effective strategy to sustain women's employment after childbirth and to narrow the motherhood gap across Europe. Moreover, our findings carry important implications for understanding the distributional consequences of the pandemic-induced shift to remote work. While the literature has documented concerns about remote work potentially exacerbating inequalities — through reduced networking opportunities, limited access to mentorship, or occupational segregation — our results suggest that for mothers specifically, the benefits in terms of employment participation outweigh these potential costs, at least in the short to medium term. This points to a more nuanced picture of remote work's impact on labour market stratification: different demographic groups may experience gains and losses along different dimensions. Future research should explore whether the employment gains we document come at the expense of other career outcomes, such as wage growth, promotion rates, or occupational mobility, and

whether these trade-offs differ across skill levels and sectors. Moreover, among the dimensions studied (employment, wages, working hours), future research should also address workers well-being and mental health among parents, mothers in particular.

Finally, the structural nature of the motherhood penalty documented in prior literature — driven by career interruptions, human capital depreciation, sector sorting, and health-related exits — suggests that remote work addresses only one piece of a complex puzzle. While our evidence shows that locational flexibility can substitute for temporal inflexibility and help mothers maintain employment continuity, it does not directly tackle other mechanisms underlying the motherhood penalty, such as employer discrimination, the wage costs of working for lower-productivity firms, or the long-term health consequences of childbearing. The persistence of gaps in desired versus actual hours even after accounting for remote work indicates that mothers continue to face constraints — whether from unequal domestic responsibilities, school disruptions, or employer expectations — that limit their ability to fully realize their labour market potential. A comprehensive policy approach must therefore combine workplace flexibility with complementary interventions, including affordable childcare, parental leave policies that encourage more equal sharing of care responsibilities between parents, and measures to combat employer discrimination against mothers.

References

Arntz, M., S. B. Yahmed, and F. Berlingieri (2022): “Working from home, hours worked and wages: Heterogeneity by gender and parenthood,” *Labour Economics*, 76, 102169.

Barrero, J. M., N. Bloom, and S. J. Davis (2021): “Why working from home will stick,” *National Bureau of Economic Research*, 10.3386/w28731.

Bisello, M., E. Peruffo, E. Fernández-Macías, and R. Rinaldi (2019): “How computerisation is transforming jobs: Evidence from the Eurofound’s European Working Conditions Survey,” *Joint Research Centre, European Commission*.

Bloom, N., G. B. Dahl, and D.-O. Rooth (2024): “Work from home and disability employment,” Technical Report 32943, National Bureau of Economic Research.

Buzard, K., L. K. Gee, and O. Stoddard (2025): “Who you gonna call? gender inequality in external demands for parental involvement,” *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, qjaf027.

Dingel, J. I., and B. Neiman (2020): “How Many Jobs Can be Done at Home?” *National Bureau of Economic Research*, 10.3386/w26948.

Fernandez-Macías, E. (2018): “Automation, digitalisation and platforms: Implications for work and employment,” *Eurofund*, 10.2806/090974.

Goldin, C. (2021): *Career & Family*: Princeton University Press.

Goldin, C., and L. Katz (2016): “A most egalitarian profession: Pharmacy and the evolution of a family-friendly occupation,” *Journal of Labor Economics*, 34, 705–746.

_____ (2022): “Understanding the economic impact of COVID-19 on women,” *National Bureau of Economic Research*, 10.3386/w29974.

Gupta, A., V. Mittal, and S. Van Nieuwerburgh (2025): “Work from home and the office real estate apocalypse,” *American Economic Review*, n.a. – n.a.

Harrington, E., and M. E. Kahn (2025): “Has the rise of work from home reduced the motherhood penalty in the labor market?” *National Bureau of Economic Research*, 10.3386/w34147.

International Labour Organization (2020): “COVID-19: Guidance for labour statistics data collection: defining and measuring remote work, telework, work at home and home-based work,” Technical report, International Labour Organization.

Kouki, A. (2023): “Beyond the “comforts” of work from home: Child health and the female wage penalty,” *European Economic Review*, 157, 104527.

Kubinec, R., J. Barcelo, R. Goldszmidt et al. (2025): “Cross-National Measures of the Intensity of COVID-19 Public Health Policies,” *The Journal of Politics*, 87, 1623–1627.

Luca, D., C. Özgüzel, and Z. Wei (2025): “The new geography of remote jobs in Europe,” *Regional Studies*, 59, 2352526.

Lyttelton, T., E. Zang, and K. Musick (2022): “Telecommuting and gender inequalities in parents’ paid and unpaid work before and during the COVID-19 pandemic,” *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 84, 230–249.

_____ (2023): “Parents’ work arrangements and gendered time use during the COVID19 pandemic,” *Journal of Marriage and Family*, 85, 657–673.

Nagler, M., J. Rincke, and E. Winkler (2024): “Working from home, commuting, and gender,” *Journal of Population Economics*, 37, 1–23.

Pouliakas, K., and J. Branka (2020): “EU jobs at highest risk of COVID-19 social distancing: Will the pandemic exacerbate labour market divide?” *IZA Discussion Papers*.

Sostero, M., S. Milasi, J. Hurley, E. Fernandez-Macias, and M. Bisello (2023): “Teleworkability and the COVID-19 crisis: potential and actual prevalence of remote work across Europe,” *IZA Journal of Labor Policy*, 13, 1–26.

Spitz-Oener, A. (2006): “Technical change, job tasks, and rising educational demands: Looking outside the wage structure,” *Journal of Labor Economics*, 24, 235–270.

Appendix

Table A.1. Effect of telework on the full-time motherhood gap, by age of youngest child

	0-2	3-5	6-8	9-11	12-14
WFH (pp) × Post	-0.02 (0.02)	0.04 (0.03)	0.03* (0.02)	0.01 (0.02)	0.01 (0.01)
Dependent mean	-0.09	-0.11	-0.09	-0.07	-0.06
Observations	55,137	56,247	56,325	56,435	56,399
KP rk Wald F (robust)	10.77	10.72	10.68	10.95	10.65

Notes: Each column estimates the effect of a 5 pp increase in WFH on the mother– non-mother full-time gap within the indicated age band of the youngest child. The endogenous regressor is WFH (pp) × Post, instrumented by (i) teleworkability × national business restrictions and (ii) low social interaction × restrictions. Controls are age, immigrant status, tertiary education, income decile, and degree of urbanization; region × and year fixed effects; standard errors clustered by country. Dependent means are pre-pandemic (2015–2019) running averages in percentage points. Stars: * <0.10, ** <0.05, *** <0.01.

Table A.2. Effect of telework on the actual weekly hours motherhood gap, by age of youngest child

	0-2	3-5	6-8	9-11	12-14
WFH (pp) × Post	6.54**	1.55*	1.93**	0.95*	0.19
	(3.07)	(0.78)	(0.70)	(0.47)	(0.30)
Dependent mean	-8.41	-2.37	-1.37	-1.09	-0.70
Observations	55,098	56,196	56,304	56,381	56,372
KP rk Wald F (robust)	10.76	10.70	10.68	10.76	10.66

Notes: Each column estimates the effect of a 5 pp increase in WFH on the mother-non-mother gap in weekly hours within the indicated age band of the youngest child. The endogenous regressor is WFH (pp) × Post, instrumented by (i) teleworkability × national business restrictions and (ii) low social interaction × restrictions. Controls are age, immigrant status, tertiary education, income decile, and degree of urbanization; region × and year fixed effects, standard errors clustered by country. Dependent means are pre-pandemic (2015-2019) running averages in percentage points. Stars: * <0.10, ** <0.05, *** <0.01.

Table A.3. Effect of telework on the permanent-job motherhood gap, by age of youngest child

	0-2	3-5	6-8	9-11	12-14
WFH (pp) × Post	-0.03 (0.02)	-0.01 (0.01)	-0.00 (0.01)	-0.01 (0.02)	-0.01 (0.01)
Dependent mean	-0.01	-0.03	-0.02	-0.01	0.01
Observations	53,249	54,395	54,494	54,511	54,251
KP rk Wald F (robust)	9.75	9.80	9.75	10.39	9.75

Notes: Each column estimates the effect of a 5 pp increase in WFH on the mother-non-mother full-time gap within the indicated age band of the youngest child. The endogenous regressor is WFH (pp) × Post, instrumented by (i) teleworkability × national business restrictions and (ii) low social interaction × restrictions. Controls are age, immigrant status, tertiary education, income decile, and degree of urbanization; region × and year fixed effects; standard errors clustered by country. Dependent means are pre-pandemic (2015-2019) running averages in percentage points. Stars: * <0.10, ** <0.05, *** <0.01.

Figure A.1. Changes in working from home by year: doctors vs. secretaries

Notes: For each occupation, points plot the annual change in the share reporting “mainly working from home” relative to 2015; vertical bars are 95% confidence intervals. Estimates come from cell-level regressions with year dummies (2015 base) and are aggregated across regions within each occupation. Cells with fewer than 50 observations are excluded; averages are weighted by cell size. Source: Authors’ calculations using the EU-LFS, 2015–2023.

paths2include.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No Project 101094626. *Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. The European Union cannot be held responsible for them. The deliverable is under review by the European Commission.*

Consortium members

OSLOMET

OSLO METROPOLITAN UNIVERSITY
STORBYUNIVERSITETET

arco

Contact

Sara Ayllón, University of Girona
sara.ayllon@udg.edu